

The Center for Open Science's Response to the Office of Management and Budget Proposed Rule: Regulation for Financial Assistance (Docket OMB-2026-0034)

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We are writing today on behalf of the [Center for Open Science](#) (COS), a non-profit organization dedicated to increasing the openness, integrity, and trustworthiness of research. Advancing these principles is foundational to ensuring science can effectively serve the public good. Our advocacy efforts are rooted in our experience as: (a) an infrastructure provider through the Open Science Framework (OSF), which supports sharing of research plans, outputs, and outcomes across the research lifecycle; (b) an organization that performs research on research to understand contributors to reproducibility, efficiency, and integrity; and (c) policy experts in practices and processes that increase the openness, rigor, and reproducibility of scientific research. This work positions COS as an expert in policies promoting the transparency, accountability, and efficiency of scientific research, including tenets of the Executive Order on Restoring Gold Standard Science (GSS).¹ Through this lens, we comment on the Office of Management and Budget's (OMB) Proposed Rule: Regulation for Federal Financial Assistance, with particular attention to Federally funded research and development.

OMB's justification for the proposed revisions to title 2 of the Code of Federal Regulations (2 CFR) is to increase the transparency, accountability, and oversight of Federal awards. Several of the proposed changes, however, undermine this goal and are at odds with the administration's stated priorities around advancing GSS, as articulated in the Office of Science and Technology Policy's (OSTP) implementation guidance.² Our comments are organized into two themes. This document supplements COS's comments to OMB with additional analysis and citations. **COS opposes OMB's proposed updates discussed throughout our comments and strongly recommends OMB retain those provisions' original language.**

¹ See May 2025 Executive Order on Restoring Gold Standard Science:
<https://www.federalregister.gov/d/2025-09802>

² See the June 23, 2025 White House Office of Science and Technology Policy (OSTP) Memorandum:
<https://www.whitehouse.gov/wp-content/uploads/2025/03/OSTP-Guidance-for-GSS-June-2025.pdf>

The regulation compromises the independence and integrity of Federally funded research by introducing senior political officials into the review and decision-making process.

§200.202, §200.205, and §200.340 embed political influence across the grant lifecycle — from deciding what grant opportunities are available, how applicants are evaluated, and whether awards are canceled on broad discretionary grounds. Placing this control in political hands forces the research timeline onto the timeline of politics, which can shift quickly, regardless of the evidence. This unpredictability is incompatible with rigorous research, creating the conditions under which researchers may fear that they — or their institutions — will be penalized if their findings prove politically inconvenient.

§200.202

Federal agencies have long designed funding programs to advance strategic objectives in the public interest, often in consultation with senior political appointees and in line with congressional appropriations. OMB's rationale for the proposed change is to "ensure that programs align with law and Executive Branch policy," while striking statutory references in the text.³ The original §200.202 required alignment with the agency's performance plan, the Program Management Improvement Accountability Act (PMIAA), and the Foundations for Evidence-Based Policymaking Act ("the Evidence Act"). In their stead, OMB references alignment with "administration policies and priorities," which can shift without notice, documentation, or consultation.

These changes are unnecessary and run counter to OMB's stated goal. The existing statutory references already ensure programs align with law and policy. The Evidence Act requires agencies publish a four-year evidence-building plan as part of their strategic planning process. This plan is developed in consultation with external stakeholders and identifies the priority questions the agency intends to address. The PMIAA similarly directs agencies toward standardized, multi-year program-management planning. Together, these statutes require agencies to document and publish their multi-year direction, enabling the research community to anticipate priority research directions, develop programs of work accordingly, and invest in the multi-year efforts that rigorous research requires.

Removing these references does not relieve agencies of their statutory obligations; it does, however, signal a shift in what OMB treats as the organizing principle for how Federal

³ See: <https://www.federalregister.gov/d/2026-10817/p-92>

programs are designed. By deprioritizing documented, multi-year plans in favor of “administration policies and priorities” that can shift without notice, the rule may leave grantees unable to reliably know what an agency prioritizes, undercutting the long-term planning that produces rigorous research and results.

§200.205

§200.205 defines merit review as “an objective process of evaluating Federal award applications in accordance with the written standards of the Federal agency.” Pre-issuance review, however, introduces subjective and political standards into the review process, including alignment with the “President’s policy priorities” and adherence to vague and unevenly applied “Gold Standard Science” criteria. In fact, §200.205(c) undermines the GSS tenet of “subject to unbiased peer review,” noting senior appointees “must not ministerially ratify or routinely defer to the recommendations of others, but must instead use their independent judgment.” In its GSS guidance, OSTP instructs agencies to “ensure appropriate reviewer selection, prioritizing expertise, independence, and viewpoint diversity.”² Tasking senior appointees, who cannot be experts in all domains of research, with overriding expert review contradicts the administration's construction of GSS.

Since the Executive Order on Restoring Gold Standard Science was issued last year, COS has consistently held that no single study can satisfy all nine tenets. Treating them as a checklist for any individual research claim or study misunderstands how knowledge is generated and how the research community self-corrects. Conditioning funding on demonstrated GSS success therefore relies on an unworkable standard. Further, in analyzing agency implementation and administration references to GSS, COS has found the tenets are inconsistently understood and applied across the government. Some of this inconsistency may be attributed to an apparent lack of coordination across agencies in operationalizing definitions and sharing best practices.⁴ For instance, while transparency is a GSS tenet, the National Oceanic and Atmospheric Administration removed public access to Federally produced climate data through [Climate.gov](https://climate.gov), citing GSS as the reason for removal.⁵ In another instance, the Department of Health and Human Services cancelled nearly \$500 million worth of mRNA vaccine development activities under the Biomedical

⁴ In COS’s response to OSTP’s Request for Information on Accelerating the American Scientific Enterprise, we recommended OSTP establish a coordination body on GSS implementation through the National Science and Technology Council: https://doi.org/10.31222/osf.io/dbfy4_v1

⁵ NOAA, [Climate.gov](https://climate.gov) redirect notice to noaa.gov/climate (archived June 4, 2026): <https://web.archive.org/web/20260604000739/https://www.noaa.gov/climate>

Advanced Research and Development Authority (BARDA).⁶ The announcement cited “data show[ing] these vaccines fail to protect effectively against upper respiratory infections like COVID and flu.” The cited source is a self-published compilation of citations that originated from a book titled *Toxic Shot: Facing the Dangers of the COVID “Vaccines,”* not a systematic review or product of unbiased expert peer review.⁷ It does not meet the GSS tenets of transparency, skepticism of findings, or unbiased peer review.

The judgment of expert, independent peer reviewers is central to ensuring that the most rigorous, promising proposals are funded. By subordinating that judgment to senior appointees applying shifting and inconsistently defined criteria, §200.205 weakens the merit review process that produces trustworthy science and sound public investments.

§200.340

Multi-year awards provide researchers with stable sources of funding as they pursue their research projects. §200.340 introduces instability into this system, with the possibility of grant cancellation looming over grantees. §200.340(a)(2) enables agencies to terminate awards found to be inconsistent with “program goals, Federal agency priorities, or the national interest as they exist at the time of the termination.” As previously discussed, §200.205 empowers senior political appointees to set those “agency priorities” that can now end an award, rather than experienced career officials with extensive input from the broader community. §200.340(e) also adds a new discretionary authority to “temporarily suspend” an award for up to 90 days when an agency determines it is “in the interest of the Federal agency,” allowing funding to be frozen and work stopped on the same open-ended grounds, before any termination decision is made. Further, provisions §200.341(c) and §200.342 curb accountability measures for discretionary terminations. §200.341(c) requires only a “brief summary” and no “detailed or exhaustive analysis” for a discretionary termination; §200.342’s objection process does not extend to discretionary terminations.

These concerns are not hypothetical. Since 2025, federal agencies have issued mass cancellations, delays, and suspensions of grants, which are subject to ongoing litigation, leaving researchers in limbo, unclear whether they have the funding needed to carry out their work or not. The consequences extend to research participants themselves. Between February and August 2025, for example, 383 (roughly 1 in 30) active NIH-funded clinical trials lost funding because they were deemed misaligned with administration priorities —

⁶ See HHS press release: <https://www.hhs.gov/press-room/hhs-winds-down-mrna-development-under-barda.html>

⁷ The data are available here: <https://zenodo.org/records/15787612>

the very rationale §200.340(a)(2) would codify.⁸ More than 74,000 participants were enrolled in affected trials and may still have been receiving interventions when funding was withdrawn. Terminating research already underway on shifting priority grounds wastes substantial public investment (the 2025 terminations alone withdrew \$1.81 billion, nearly a third of it unspent), prevents research programs from delivering and publishing results, and raises serious questions about the obligations owed to participants who assumed research risk for studies that will now never reach completion.

The regulation limits the degree to which Federally funded researchers can freely and independently communicate their work, undermining OMB's stated goals of increasing transparency and accountability.

§200.432, §200.450, and §200.461 place limits on grant recipients' ability to present at conferences, communicate findings, and publish their work. These activities ensure findings reach the taxpayers funding them rather than stay locked in academic institutions.

§200.432 and §200.450

Public investments in federally funded research compounds when findings are able to extend beyond the funded team. Evidence reaches decision-makers to inform robust policy, the public enjoys and benefits from the knowledge it funded, and unanticipated collaborations spark new work. Presenting research at conferences, communicating the process and findings to the public, and briefing policymakers on the implications of discovery are core to delivering these returns. §200.432 and §200.450 restrict these activities. §200.432 conditions conference participation on prior agency approval; §200.450 limits researchers' communication in terms broad enough to reach beyond lobbying into the ordinary sharing of findings.

Conferences are where findings are presented, tested through expert feedback before and after publication, and where collaborations form. §200.432(b) introduces a provision that conference costs are only allowable if participation "is expressly approved by the Federal agency and included in the terms and conditions of the Federal award." This addition places

⁸ Patel VR, Liu M, Jena AB. Clinical Trials Affected by Research Grant Terminations at the National Institutes of Health. *JAMA Intern Med.* 2026;186(1):126–128. [doi:10.1001/jamainternmed.2025.6088](https://doi.org/10.1001/jamainternmed.2025.6088) (See also: <https://www.ajmc.com/view/nih-grant-terminations-disrupt-1-in-30-clinical-trials-impacting-over-74-000-participants>)

a discretionary gate in front of a routine and essential scientific activity, creating unnecessary burden on both grantees and agency staff.

While conferences provide a critical venue for researchers to communicate to fellow researchers, extending the returns on public investment depends on findings reaching beyond that community to inform the public and the decisions that impact them. §200.450 chills that function. §200.450 was initially designed to limit the ability of grant recipients to use their funds to lobby; it already defines and prohibits lobbying. It prohibits unallowable activity that uses grant funds to influence specific legislation, appropriations, or grant decisions, while permitting presentation of non-partisan, factual research findings to decision-makers, including testimony and responses to legislative requests.

The proposed §200.450(c)(1)(iv)-(v) introduces unnecessary confusion, extending unallowable activities to include broad, vague prohibitions on “issue advocacy or public messaging” and “messaging designed to influence public attitudes on matters not necessary to accomplish the purpose of the Federal award.” Further, science communication, or explaining research findings to non-technical audiences, is rarely *necessary* to complete a grant; rather, it is an essential ingredient for how the public realizes the benefits of their investments. This is a core motivation of federal public access policies. With the introduction of OMB’s proposed language, a researcher cannot easily tell where permissible dissemination ends and prohibited “public messaging” begins — particularly where research findings may be politically sensitive. For example, a researcher who studies the health effects of air quality may be deterred from briefing a state legislature on those findings, uncertain whether doing so would be treated as sharing research related to the award or as prohibited influence on state policymaking.

When coupled with §200.202(c), which directs agencies to avoid funding programs that create “the appearance of supporting” political advocacy or attempts to influence government officials, researchers are left without a clear standard for what they may say about their own work. The result stifles the free flow of scientific information with researchers self-censoring findings to the public and to decision-makers.

§200.461

§200.461 makes publication costs — including article processing charges (APCs) and open access fees — unallowable except where required by statute or approved by the agency on a case-by-case basis. Paragraph (b) further specifies that “a general requirement to make results publicly available must not be construed as authorizing publication costs.” This

provision is in direct conflict with agency public access policies, referenced in GSS implementation plans, which permit such costs to enable free and immediate access to research results. The provision thus leaves grantees in a difficult position of trying to comply with agency public access policies, while navigating complex publisher copyright agreements, with little resourcing or support to do so.

We are in strong support of efforts to maximize free and immediate access to Federally funded research, and share OMB's attention to financial strains placed on researchers — and indirectly on the taxpayers who fund their research — because of unreasonably high charges to publish. Barring APCs, however, does not address why journals have been able to charge such high fees in the first place, which include the pressure to "publish or perish" and consolidation across the publishing industry.

Rather than prohibiting these costs outright, agencies should invest in open research infrastructures and alternative publishing models to enable rapid dissemination of varied research outputs. The digital age has enabled researchers to share other research outputs that underlie discovery, including preregistrations, data, code, materials, preprints, and more. Preprint repository and review services, and diamond open access models, offer a cheaper alternative to Hybrid and Gold Open Access models that rely on APCs; further, open-source infrastructures enable further innovations, increasing the potential return on these investments. This approach should be paired with rethinking and supporting innovation in research assessment to shift away from publication-based metrics.

The regulation undermines OMB's stated goal of reducing administrative burden, imposing new costs that threaten the efficiency and return that Federally funded research delivers.

The current system, in which researchers exercise independent judgment and expert panels evaluate proposals on their merits, has produced tremendous value. Analysis from the Federal Reserve Bank of Dallas estimates the return on nondefense government research and development funding at 140 to 210 percent; these investments have accounted for roughly one-fifth of American business-sector productivity growth since World War II.⁹ §200.205, §200.432, and §200.461 replace this efficiency with new layers of approval and review. §200.205 requires a senior appointee to exercise "independent judgment" on every discretionary award rather than deferring to review panels, which

⁹ Fieldhouse AJ, Mertens K. The Returns to Government R&D: Evidence from U.S. Appropriations Shocks. Federal Reserve Bank of Dallas Working Paper 2305. 2024. [doi:10.24149/wp2305r2](https://doi.org/10.24149/wp2305r2)

places substantial burden on the appointees doing the review and wastes the time of reviewers invited to impart their expertise. §200.432 and §200.461 convert routine, allowable costs, such as conference participation and publication, into case-by-case approvals. These provisions consume the time of appointees, program officers, and researchers alike, while their discretionary nature leaves program officers caught between political directives and the researchers they support. The result is delay, uncertainty, and diverted effort, which translates to costs borne across the research enterprise that diminish the very return on investment the American people have come to expect.